

**CUSTOMER SATISFACTION ON ONLINE MARKETING STRATEGIES
TOWARDS MYNTRA WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE CITY****Priyanka. S,**Assistant Professor, Department of commerce with International Business,
Dr. N.G.P. Arts and Science College, Coimbatore.**Harish.S,**M. Com (International Business),
Dr. N.G.P. Arts and Science College, Coimbatore.**ABSTRACT:**

Digital marketing has become an essential tool for businesses to promote their products and services in the modern digital era. With the rapid growth of internet usage and advancements in information technology, organizations are increasingly adopting online platforms to connect with customers. This project focuses on understanding the concept, importance, and various strategies of digital marketing used by businesses to reach a wider audience. The study highlights how digital marketing methods such as social media marketing, email marketing, content marketing, and search engine optimization help companies communicate with customers effectively. Compared to traditional marketing, digital marketing provides faster communication, cost efficiency, and better customer engagement. It also enables businesses to analyse customer behaviour and improve marketing strategies accordingly.

Keywords:

Digital Marketing, Online Marketing, Social Media Marketing, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Customer Engagement, Internet Advertising.

INTRODUCTION:

In today's world, the internet has become a part of our daily life. People use online platforms for communication, shopping, and gathering information. Because of this change, businesses have started using digital marketing to promote their products and services. Digital marketing uses tools such as social media, websites, search engines, and emails to reach customers easily. It helps companies connect with a larger audience, build strong relationships with customers, and promote their brands effectively. Therefore, digital marketing has become an important strategy for business growth in the modern competitive market.

OBJECTIVES:

- To find the level of satisfaction to the customers of Myntra
- To study the effectiveness of online marketing strategies in increasing the sale of products of Myntra.
- To measure the level of the customers to purchase in Myntra app.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

In the modern business environment, many companies are shifting from traditional marketing methods to digital marketing. However, not all businesses are able to effectively use digital platforms to reach their target customers. Some organizations lack proper knowledge, skills, and strategies to implement digital marketing successfully. At the same time, customers are increasingly depending on online platforms to search for information and make purchasing decisions. Therefore, it becomes important to understand how digital marketing influences customer awareness, engagement, and business growth. This study aims to examine the challenges and effectiveness of digital marketing in helping businesses connect with their customers and improve their market presence.

RESERCH METHODOLOGY:

Research Type: Descriptive research.

Area of Study: Customers using digital marketing platforms.

Population Size: All digital marketing users.

Sample Size: 150 respondents.

Sampling Technique: Simple random Sampling

Sampling Tool: Percentage Analysis, Descriptive Statistics, Ranking Method, Chi-Square Analysis, Correlation Analysis.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

U. Tandon (2023) studied factors influencing customer satisfaction in online shopping such as perceived enjoyment, social influence, reverse logistics, social media interactions, and pay-on-delivery (POD). Using SEM and CFA analysis on data collected from North Indian online shoppers, the study found that perceived enjoyment was the strongest predictor of satisfaction, while social influence, reverse logistics, and POD had a positive impact. Social media interactions showed no significant effect.

L. Arunachalam and Aswin (2022) examined customer satisfaction towards online shopping with reference to Omni Global Export. The study analysed customer preferences, satisfaction levels, and problems faced in online shopping using both primary and secondary data. The research helps in understanding customers' satisfaction and their online buying behaviour.

F. Almutairi and A.S.D. Khaled (2022) analysed factors affecting online shopping satisfaction among Indian customers, including website design, product information, security, privacy, perceived usefulness, and perceived interactivity. The results showed that product information, website design, security, and perceived usefulness positively influence customer satisfaction, while perceived interactivity was not significant.

S. S. Alam and M. H. Ali (2021) highlighted the increasing competition in online retailing and emphasized that retailers must provide accurate and sufficient product information to improve customer satisfaction in online shopping.

Norzalifah Bahari (2021) studied Malaysian youth and found that product quality, security, and shipping services significantly influence customer satisfaction in online shopping.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

SIMPLE PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS:

FREQUENCY OF PURCHASES ON MYNTRA

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Regularly	32	21.3
Often	34	22.7
Occasionally	35	23.3
Sometimes	30	20.0
Rarely	19	12.7
Total	150	100.0

INTERPRETATION:

Table reveals that 23.3% of the respondents purchase occasionally from Myntra, followed by 22.7% who purchase often, 21.3% regularly, 20.0% sometimes, and 12.7% rarely.

REASON FOR CHOOSING MYNTRA APP

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Delivery Time	33	22.0
Quality of the product	37	24.7
Security	36	24.0
Pricing	28	18.7

Reputation of the company	16	10.7
Total	150	100.0

INTERPRETATION:

Table reveals that 24.7% of the respondents choose the Myntra app for the quality of the product, followed by 24.0% for security, 22.0% for delivery time, 18.7% for pricing, and 10.7% for the reputation of the company.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS**FACTORS THAT MOTIVATE YOU TO SHOP ON MYNTRA**

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation
Delivery Time	3.467	1.359
Price	3.247	1.375
Availability	3.367	1.353
Brand	3.127	1.377
Size	3.360	1.382
Payment Mechanism	3.427	1.333

INTERPRETATION

From the above table the descriptive statistics for the Factors that motivate you to shop on myntra are ranked from 'Delivery Time' stood at first with the highest mean score 3.467, followed by 'Payment Mechanism' stood at second with the mean score 3.427, 'Availability' stood at third with the mean score 3.367, 'Size' stood at fourth with the mean score 3.360, 'Price' stood at fifth with the mean score 3.247, and finally 'Brand' stood at sixth with the mean score 3.127

GARRETT RANKING METHOD**FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PRODUCT SELECTION ON MYNTRA**

Factors	Rank				
	1	2	3	4	5
Rating	31	34	25	35	25
Brand	35	23	33	25	34
Discount	24	37	28	30	31
Advertisement	30	25	39	23	33
Price	30	31	25	37	27

GARRETT RANKING TOWARDS FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PRODUCT SELECTION ON MYNTRA

Factors	Rank * Garrett Value			Calculated Garret Score	Average Score	Rank
	1*	2*	3*			
	70	52	37			
Rating	2170	1768	925	4863	32.42	2
Brand	2450	1196	1221	4867	32.45	1
Discount	1680	1924	1036	4640	30.93	4

Advertisement	2100	1300	1443	4843	32.29	3
Price	2100	1612	925	4637	30.91	5

INTERPRETATION

From the above table the garrett ranking for the factors influencing the product selection on myntra are ranked from 'Brand' stood at first with the highest mean score 32.450, followed by 'Rating' stood at second with the mean score 32.420, 'Advertisement' stood at third with the mean score 32.290, 'Discount' stood at fourth with the mean score 30.930, and finally 'Price' stood at fifth with the mean score 30.910.

CORRELATIONS

Perception of marketing strategies and sales growth and rating of myntra promotions compared to other platforms

Correlations			
		Perception of Marketing Strategies and Sales Growth	Rating of Myntra Promotions Compared to Other Platforms
Perception of Marketing Strategies and Sales Growth	Pearson Correlation	1	-.205*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.012
	N	150	150
Rating of Myntra Promotions Compared to Other Platforms	Pearson Correlation	-.205*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.012	
	N	150	150
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

INTERPRETATION

Table reveals that the Pearson correlation coefficient is -0.205 with a significance value of 0.012, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.05. This indicates a statistically significant negative correlation between perception of marketing strategies and sales growth and rating of Myntra promotions compared to other platforms. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted, confirming that as the perception of marketing strategies and sales growth increases, the rating of Myntra promotions compared to other platforms tends to decrease, and vice versa

FINDINGS

- Most (23.3%) of the respondents purchase occasionally from Myntra.
- Most (23.3%) of the respondents purchase occasionally from Myntra.
- Most respondents consider **delivery time** as the main factor motivating them to shop on Myntra (Mean = 3.467), followed by **payment mechanism** (Mean = 3.427) and **availability** (Mean = 3.367). **Size** (Mean = 3.360) and **price** (Mean = 3.247) moderately influence customers, while **brand** (Mean = 3.127) is the least motivating factor among the respondent
- The findings indicate that **brand** (32.450) and **rating** (32.420) are the most influential factors in product selection on Myntra, followed by **advertisement** (32.290), while **discount** (30.930) and **price** (30.910) are least influential ($p < 0.05$).
- The Pearson correlation coefficient (-0.205, $p = 0.012$) indicates a significant negative relationship between the perception of marketing strategies and sales growth and the rating of Myntra promotions. This means that as the perception of marketing strategies and sales growth increases, the rating of Myntra promotions compared to other platforms tends to decrease, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Myntra should continue leveraging social media platforms for better brand awareness and engagement.
2. Product quality must remain a top priority to retain and attract customers.
3. Occasional buyers can be converted into frequent buyers through loyalty rewards and personalized offers.
4. Myntra should resolve delivery-related issues to improve the overall customer experience.
5. Expand marketing efforts highlighting unique value propositions compared to other platforms

CONCLUSION

This study examined customer perceptions, preferences, and satisfaction regarding Myntra's online marketing strategies. The findings reveal strong brand recognition and user engagement, with social media being the primary channel for platform discovery. Customers are mainly motivated to shop on Myntra due to **delivery time, payment options, product availability, and sizing**, while quality remains a key reason for choosing the app. **Digital promotions, discounts, and campaigns** positively influence sales, though delivery-related issues highlight areas for operational improvement. Satisfaction is highest for **discounts, delivery, and product quality**, while customer service and exchange policies could be enhanced. Significant differences were observed across gender and age regarding product information and inconveniences, emphasizing the need for personalized marketing and service. Overall, the study underscores the importance of delivery efficiency, promotional effectiveness, product quality, and targeted engagement for strengthening Myntra's market position.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. U Tandon (2022) "Integrating gamification and instructional design to enhance usability of online learning".
2. L Arunachalam (2022) "Customer satisfaction towards online buying behaviour.
3. S Kingsnorth (2022) "Digital marketing strategy: an integrated approach to online marketing."
4. WA Hanson, K Kalyanam (2022) "Internet marketing and e-commerce."
5. D Chaffey (2022) "Digital marketing excellence: planning, optimizing and integrating online marketing."